

Ethno-Religious Conflict: The Bane Of Nigeria Unity

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Abstract

Ethno-Religious conflict refers to the manifestation of ethnocentrism and religious bigotry in Nigeria society, which over the years have been the bane of Nigeria unity. Though religion has played vital role in the society, and has contributed immensely to the national development of this country. It has also been wrongly used by some ethnic groups to afflict this country severally with conflicts leading to wanton destruction of properties and loss of human lives. Obviously, there has been too much blood letting in this country resulting from ethnic and religious conflict which is threatening the very foundation of Nigeria's corporate existence as a nation. The menace of ethno-religious conflict in Nigeria is fast eroding the core socio-cultural and religious value which forbids murder, covetousness, falsehood etc. It has hampered the economic growth of this country to such a great extent that poverty has engulfed the majority of the citizen. Worst still the mayhems have produced many disabled persons, orphans and widows, it has robbed many, of their comfortable homes, jobs and careers; it has left the citizens with enduring sorrow very hard to contend with. This research is set out to establish that ethnic and religious conflicts constitute a hitch to national integration. The researcher adopted historical research method. The findings made clear the fact that the peace and love which is the core religious value has not been exploited.

Keywords: Ethno-Religion, Conflict, Unity

Introduction

Beginning from the colonial era the unity of Nigeria has been greatly threatened by series of crisis. Most of these crises hinges on ethnocentrism and religious bigotry. It may not be surprise that in multi ethnic and multi- religious nation like Nigeria there could be cultural competitions, religious rivalry and political intrigue. Rather what is surprise is the level of

damages that has resulted from such competitions.

It is expected that a country with such diversities as Nigeria will be economically advantageous and politically great. Unfortunately, the inability of the various ethnic and religious groups to embrace themselves has retarded economic growth, inhibited cultural assimilations among different groups thereby hindering national integration. It is worrisome particularly as the conflicts have no sign of ending in the near future.

This research paper is an attempt to specifically show that ethno-religious conflict is a monster that is responsible for Nigeria woes. It gives foreign investors a real scare when human lives are wasted with impunity, thereby hindering foreign investments in Nigeria. The havoc of ethno-religious conflicts is manifested in the overall backwardness of Nigeria development, as will be portrayed in this work. The purpose of enumerating the ills of this cankerworm is to correct the bad impressions which ethnic and religious sentiments may have generated, and to buttress the fact that, the nation building remains the prime agenda in democratic government. Immediately after the introduction, is the elucidation of the concepts used, Ethno-religious conflicts: an overview, mode of operations, implications of the ethno-religious conflicts, recommendation and conclusion.

Clarification of Concepts

Ethno-religious conflicts,

For clarity, conflicts should first be understood to mean disagreement between two opposing opinions or principles. Often times it manifests in the way of political, ethnic and religious difference. Ethno-religious Conflict refers to a situation where a community of people uses both ethnicity and religion simultaneously in a struggle for supremacy of

race, belief and power. “In some cases, it can be seen as a social construct where individuals are incited to accept ethnic/religious identity to express who they are and what they want.

In the Nigerian context, ethnic and religious differences form sentiments which override perceptions of nationalism” (Osukwu 2014). Thus, both the ruler and the ruled are stuck in a political quagmire, swaying uncertainly in absolute distraction as competition for regional hegemony is given prime concern at the expense of national interest. Hence people are programmed for silly sentimental politics by persons who aim to perpetuate themselves in power; what a bizarre strategy.

Unity

A nation can only and truly be one when the nationalist concept is upheld over and above ethnic/religious sentiments. Speaking in Calabar, at the retreat held by the Southern Senators’ forum, Senate President, Bukola Saraki said, “As nation, unity is a prerequisite for development, stability and greatness’ (Daily Trust may 16 2018). Ironically, unity is often mistaken for uniformity. Uniformity is being the same or having no difference and not changing. By implication the culture, language and religion, must be one; in other words it is an effort to

create one type of religio-cultural environment in a pluralistic society. This kind of environment can only be possible in Nigeria through pogrom.

Unity as conceived by the Nigeria pan-nationalists is unity of purpose which “entails togetherness based on full and harmonious agreement of all involved, with all freedom of will and intention” (Ezeanya 2016: 158). This allows for socio-cultural and ethno-religious diversity. This was the wish of Zik of Africa who fought to achieve political independence for Nigeria. This was echoed by Oritsejafor (2014: 2) thus, “Dr. Azikiwe believed in a Nigeria with a strong nationalist spirit in which every part of the nation would be home for all without recourse to his ethnic, religious and sectional identities, enjoying an all time equal freedom of speech, equal freedom of association and equal freedom of religious worship”.

This dream of ‘our hero’s past’ seems to be a mirage in Nigeria where citizens are divided along ethnic and religious inclination. The identification of citizens by the use of North and South, or Islam and Christian is a serious threat to national unity. A county where job appointments, school admissions and military recruitments are based on ones ethnic or religious background is a caricature of true

federalism. Unfortunately, Nigeria has produced more sectional leaders whose concerns are parochial. Hence, complaint for marginalization by various groups is growing unabated. It was only during the civil war that Nigeria got united to finish the perceived enemy “Biafra”. Since the civil war Nigeria has sunk deeper into a quagmire of ethno-religious violence and lawlessness, preceding this was series of military coup, and today Nigeria is being confronted by insurgency, militancy, and agitation. The recent public outcry of ethnic cleansing by T.Y Danjuma, suffices it that there is a crisis of confidence among Nigerians. This case is fundamental and has remained unresolved. To understand the root cause of the problem one has to trace the event that gave birth to Nigeria.

Formation of Nigeria Nation: An Overview

Nigeria is a combination of multi-ethnic groups, which by the discretion of the British government came into existence as a sovereign nation with the amalgamation of North and Southern Protectorate on 1st day of January 1914. Prior to the amalgamation of Nigeria the various nations, kingdoms and empires that were merged to form a political unit now known as Nigeria formerly existed independently, each having different behavioural traits, different cultural values and different concept of government. For

instance, the Igbo are egalitarians and so ran a democratic system of government. The Yoruba are monarchists and have developed for themselves different autonomous royal stools before the colonization, while the Fulani are imperialist whose perception about government differs considerably with other Nigerians. The Fulani mentality about government is to have dominion over other nations using Islam to seal the fate of their subjects. These differences posed a challenge to the amalgamation. In addition to these challenges is the penetration of the two foreign religions into Nigeria, which hold widely divergent opinion about life.

Islam and Christianity had in the first half of the nineteenth century been firmly established in Nigeria. Islam hoisted its flag in the North and Christianity in the South with same intention to spread out to the opposite directions. Thus, like a vehicles coming from opposite direction they hit head-on and fell into the centre of the country. Oritsejafor (2014: 5) further elucidated this fact when he said,

On the eve of British colony encounter with the present people of Nigeria, two events, both religiously inclined, which were to later become the pivotal basis of national conflict were taking place in swift succession; one coming through the Sahara Desert and the other coming through the Atlantic Ocean. Both events were to later clash at

a spot which seems to be the equidistance between what are today defined as Northern and Southern Nigeria.

The foreign religions had the same measure of desperation the colonial power had to occupy Nigeria. The competitive nature of these religions coupled with their fruitful years of missionary endeavour moved Nigeria into religious pluralism. The colonial administrators were aware of the number of religions in Nigeria but accorded formal recognition to Islam and Christianity only. Thenceforth, clerics of both religions were involved in the governance of the protectorates, an apparent show of colonial government's preference for the Islam and Christianity over the traditional religion. Any resistance from the traditional religion attracted the colonial administration, which used force against it and destroyed some of its powerful deities. This premised the first sectarian crisis between the adherents of the foreign religions and the natives. Traditional religion would have been annihilated but for its dynamism, has continued to exist.

Consequent upon demystification of traditional environment became porous for the alien religions to thrive. Unfortunately, the core religious values which is embedded on the golden rule "love for one another" and "peace with all men", have not been explored. Rather too much

emphasis has often been on the differences instead of the similarities. The religious fundamentalists, seems not be interested in integration, rather huge interest is on the uniqueness of the particular religion extremists believe and promote. For instance, there is this caution in the Bible

Do not be yoked together with unbelievers. For what partnership have righteousness and iniquity? Or what fellowship has light with darkness? What accord has Christ with Baal? Or what has a believer in common with an unbeliever? What agreement has the temple of God with idols? For we are the temple of the Holy Spirit; as God said, "I will live in them and move among them, and I will be their God, and they shall be my people. Therefore, come out from them, and be separated from them, says the Lord, and touch nothing unclean; then I will welcome you" (2corinthian 6:14-17).

The above quotation is the reason a Christian fanatics would not want to associate with people of other faith. It forbids a Christian believer from meddling with unbeliever. The warning is a very serious one particularly as it has the promise of welcoming of the believer in heaven. The fact that no believer want to go to hell is also the reason why no fanatic would disobey Biblical instructions such as this.

On the other hand, Quran enjoins Muslims to kill the unbelievers (non-Muslims); this is

contained in Surat 9 verse 5. It is rendered thus "When the sacred months are over, then fight and slay the pagans wherever you find them; And seize them beleaguer them, And lie in wait for them in every stratagem (of war); But if they repent and establish regular prayers and practice regular charity, then open the way for them: "For God is oft-forgiving, most merciful".

Thus the Quran urges the Muslims to fight in the name of God. This fight is call jihad "holy war". According to Global Jihad Network, "Jihad is the obligation of each Muslim, within his abilities, to spread Islam in the world and it supposes to last up to the day that the last non-Muslim human being recognizes Islam as the true faith". Nzomiwi (1989: 113) quipped that "the above quotation from the Quran is enough to show that jihad of the sword rest on direct command of the Quran, and that any Muslim who dies in such a war would win a crown of martyrdom". Akuma (2004: 29) noted that "This militant disposition in Islam is an avowed conversion mechanism which has helped Islam in no small measure.

This is the reason Muslim fanatics are unleashing mayhems on the Nigeria citizens who, they consider to be infidels. From 1804, when Jihad was declared against the infidel (non-Muslims) there have been cases of persecution, oppression, murder and out brake of wars.

The effect of Jihad in the North West was the subjugation of Hausa tribal groups which according to Buah (1977: 113) transformed into Fulani Empire and a caliphate, with its headquarters at Sokoto". However, the war against the infidel (non-Muslims) by the Fulani Jihadist failed woefully in the North East as they were defeated on the battle-field by the great Kenembu warrior, Muhammed ibn el-Kanemi and that stopped Muhammed Bello's ambition of extending the Sokoto Caliphate to North East (Oritsejafor 2014). Apart from the Hausa tribal group, no other one was assimilated into Fulani tribal group, not even the non Hausa city within the Sokoto Caliphate. Holding this same view Oritsejafor (2014: 6) stated inter alia,

Within the very vicinity of the headquarters of Sokoto Caliphate, the people of the great fishing city of Argungu, living less than one hundred kilometres away, had severally confirmed their independence through successive defeat of the armies of the Sokoto Caliphate. The same situation applies to the people of what is today called the Zuru Emirate of Kebbi State made up of Dakarkari and other allied non-Hausa-Fulani ethnic groups. This explains why the Zuru Emirate which lies within the core-Caliphate zone remains predominantly Christians in religion today.

Similarly, the jihadists' frantic efforts to colonize the Middle Belt proved futile. Each time the Jihadists attacked, there was always a reprisal attack by the Middle Belterns. This again explains why it was easy for Christian missionaries to penetrate into these areas and consequently planted Christianity among these people". Hence it has become difficult for the Fulani to foist Islam on them as was done to the Hausa. Writing on this Oritsejafor (2014: 6) remarked that,

On the whole, much of what is today known as the middle belt running horizontally from the present southern part of Kebbi State, through the defunct Southern Zaria Province, Southern Bauchi and much of the present Gombe State, to the Bama-Chibok periphery of the present south part of Bornu State, and standing to vertically to the present Plateau, Nasarawa, Kogi, Adamawa, Taraba and Benue State including the Federal Capital Territory were never under the Sokoto Caliphate on the eve of the British conquest of the North.

In the South West the Fulani Jihadists' attempt to take over Yoruba kingdoms was foiled because the Yoruba armies fiercely resisted them. Orisejafor (2014: 6) captured the event thus, "The re-invigorated Oyo army led by the great city of Ibadan had marched against the invading Fulani forces and handed them a crushing defeat thereby putting the idea of a Fulani Empire extending

beyond the Yoruba city of Ilorin on the stable of illusion”.

Nevertheless, “The Muslim community in the North gained immensely with the advent of the colonial administration” (Ene 2004: 50). Islam thrived during the colonial era because the introduction of indirect rule empowered the Emirs to rule the North on behalf of the colonial masters. An opportunity the Emirs maximized for the enlargement of their empire. Obiezuofu-Ezeigbo (2007: 4) gave reason for the use of indirect rule to include, “its cheapness in relation to the manpower shortage, continuity in administration of the government with its attended peace and stability”. The system alas, encouraged the continued subjugation of the Hausa and other minority groups whose struggle to regain independence from the Fulani invaders was truncated by that process. Hence, (Yusuf, 2012: 6) inferred that, “The introduction of indirect rule institutionalised the inferiority status for the non-Muslim peoples of the Middle Belt”. The International Crisis Group Report (2012: 6) captures the event thus:

British rule empowered the Hausa/Fulani community to subjugate the indigenes, and, by so doing, established the hegemony of the north over the country – which jihad could not have achieve because Islamisation of the Middle Belt had failed. Marginalization and oppression had driven

those minorities to embrace Christianity as a tool for political emancipation. Middle Belt Muslims have also complained of treatment as second class citizens by Hausa-Fulani Muslims.

Oritsejiafor (2014: 6) lamented that Lord Lugard’s decision to empower the defeated Caliphate beyond even the territorial gains of the jihad, as well as reinstate the defeated Kanembu dynasty was later to become one of the fundamental banes of our polity today”, he concluded that, “the nationalism in Nigeria today is built on the political foundation of two conflicting colonialism – one internal represented by the Sokoto Caliphate of the Hausa-Fulani the coming the religion of Islam with its primary allegiance to Islamic Middle East; the other being external represented by the British Empire which equally came with its enlivening religion Christianity” (p. 9). The effort to abolish any form of colonialism and enthrone nationalism and the struggle to remain status quo is reason for the ethno-religious conflict in Nigeria. It is so because according to Uka (2008: 3) “Our erstwhile colonial master left us with politics of ethnic and religious conflict that has plagued the nation since its inception”.

Mode of Ethno-Religious Conflict

Ethno-Religious Conflict appears in various modes as will be highlighted in this work. It is a power play for supremacy using

ethnicity and religion simultaneously to press home demand. Such phenomenon thrives in a society where faith is adopted for identification of member. The identification of a citizen of Nigeria is determined by a number of factors of which ethnic and religion are paramount. While filling a form for admission, employment or promotion, a Nigerian is required to write his/her names, origin and religion. By that one could easily gain favour or fall prey to ethno-religious marginalization. Political machinery is a great asset to advance groups ambition. Therefore, persecution, intrigue, and physical combat are veritable instruments of ethno-religious conflicts. It is not difficult in Nigeria to distinguish between the Northerner and the Southerner; it is even easier to distinguish between a Muslim and a Christian. With this sharp distinction the north and the south became deeply suspicious of one another. "Thus, politics in the first Republic was not only based on ethnic and religious tendencies, but was dominated by powerful ethnic personalities" (Uka 2008: 4).

The emphasis on ethno-religious differences has been a political strategy used in Nigeria to manipulate the nation's politics. It is applied in the form of divide and rule and this works against patriotic nationalism in the nation's politics (Osukwu 2014). This led to

dichotomy which Osukwu, referred to as divide and rule when he said.

The divide and rule policy started during the colonial era. It ignited ethnic consciousness and ushered in separation. There were two colonial policies: namely the Land and Native Rights Ordinance initiated in 1910 and the Sabongari policy. These policies initiated a social division existing between the north and southern Nigeria. In practical sense, the policies overlook the similarities among the people and lay emphasis on their differences. Overtime, the effects of this emphasis have been negative forces which produce trails of destructive violence and threat to the nation's territorial integrity. The Ogoni-Andoni, Jukun-Tiv, Hausa-Mambilla and a host of other blood-lettings are aftermaths of the above said policies. They encourage urban-based segregations. Then the ethnic massacre of the Igbos living in the north preceded the civil war of 1967-70

Recognising the schism earlier on, Herbert Macaulay regretted that "As Africans, we have been split almost into smithereens by what we call religion in West Africa" (cited in Ody 2000: 7). The effort to realise a united Nigeria was and is still being challenged by this identity syndrome. It is therefore, not surprise that in 1953, when Nigerians were given opportunity to decide on

their future, Northern delegates lead by the Sardauna expressed their opposition to self government. Earlier on in 1942, the northern Emirs while responding to UK base West African Student Union who solicited for their support against colonial rule in Nigeria said, "Holding this country together is not possible except by means of the religion of the Prophet. If they want political unity, let them follow our religion" (cited in Awolowo 1947: 51).

The use of religion as identity and the outright intolerance of other religion by the extremists is the cause of the disunity in Nigeria. There is an evidence of the inhuman treatment meted out to non Muslim in the North. for instance, Stephen Adefila a permanent secretary in Kwara State was compulsorily retired for preaching the gospel at Kabba, on "Light and Darkness" at a 3-days revival in January 1980 without due process (Adefila 2000). Ejoor (1989: 12), also recounted how examination was "conducted in Hausa language in the Army, which gave his junior Gowon advantage over him".

The use of political machinery

It is not exaggeration to say that religious extremists and tribal leaders make the worst form of leadership. They are sentimental and cover corruption with religion and use politics to promote faith. They have no regard for other religion, it dismays that the poor

citizen play into their hand. The statement that Nigeria is a circular state is jettisoned. For instance, "in 1986 action was taken by the Northern Muslims in the corridor of power against none Muslim Nigerians, by registering Nigeria in the membership of Organization of Islamic Conference (OIC)" (Ody 200: 27). This single action exposed the calculated attempt of the Muslim North to Islamize Nigeria, and if not checked might plug the country into chaos. Hence, Adinuba (2014) cautioned that:

Every Nigerian must be worried by the current mindless promotion of religious bigotry. Faith is founded on the most powerful sentiments in human beings, and not reason or rationality. Divisive politics based on religion has proved to be most destructive in human history. Religious politics manipulation by the late Jafar el Nimriery from 1973 destroyed the Sudan, eventually leading to its breakup in 2011. Religious politics was responsible for the Balkan War which broke up Yugoslavia in the 1990s into three different countries. Religious politics led to the carving out of East Timor from Indonesia in 2002. Religious politics held Northern Ireland down for decades until the Good Friday Agreement of 1998 promoted by United States President Bill Clinton led to the enthronement of reason. Religious politics between Christians and Muslims is responsible for the ongoing carnage in the Central African Republic.

Religious Crisis in Nigeria

The first ethno-religious conflict in Nigeria dates back to 1953 when the southern delegates clashed with the Northerners in Kano, over the motion for self government in 1956 moved by Anthony Enahoro and the counter motion by Sir Ahumadu Bello. In 1996, Igbo were massacred in the North; the pogrom forced the South East to secede. “The pattern of destruction, for example, was the same all over the northern towns the riots visited. The riots were known as Araba Riots, for the war cry was of the rioters was “Araba” which in Hausa language means “secession” (Okonkwo2003: 1). the rioters at this particular point were apparently anxious to secede.

Ten years after the civil war Nigeria unexpectedly moved into the decades of religious intolerance. The Islamic jihadist came up again with different style of attack on the perceived infidels (unbelievers). It was Maitatsine who opened the new chapter of religious violence in Kano, in 1980. In the first two decade (1980s and 1990s) of violence Izala Muslim sect and the Shiites joined in act of lawlessness. The table below shows the dates, place and sates where the incidents happened, also contained in the table is the Muslim sect responsible for the attack, the casualty and effect and effects of the attack and the source of information.

Table

s/n	Date	Place	State	The attacker	Casualty/effects	Source
1	/12/1980	Kano	Kano	Maitatsine	4,900	Newswatch 30/3/1987,p.6
2	30/10/1982	Maiduguri	Borno	Maitatsine	400	African Concord 24/3/1987,p.25
3	27/2/1984	Jimeta	Gongola	Maitatsine	763 people killed, 3500, building damaged,30people made homeless, Yola modern market destroyed.	National Concord, 24/3/1987,p.27
4	26/4/1985	Gombe	Bauchi	Maitatsine	120 people killed, police lost 11 rifles, 7,231 rounds of ammunition, 69 some	Newswatch, 30/3/1987,p.25

					cartridges, five glass grenades and six rifle magazines to the fanatics.	
5	5/5/1986	Unibadan	Oyo	Muslim Fanatics	Christian statue burnt	African Concord, 5/2/1990,p.32
6	8/3/1988	Kaduna Polytechnic	Kaduna	Muslim students	Church building was pulled down	Newswatch, 28/3/1988,p.25
7	13/6/88	Ahmadu Bello university, Zaria	Kaduna	Muslim students	Over one hundred students were injured	Newswatch, 27/6/1988,p.38
8	22/4/1991	Tafawa Belewa	Bauchi	Muslim butcher	28 churches, other properties belonging to Christians including living houses were burnt	Today's Challenge, No.2. 1991,p.6
9	14/10/1991	Kano	Kano	Muslim Fanatics	Over one thousand people were killed, many churches burnt. Reihard Boke's crusade was disrupted	Today's Challenge, No.1. 1991,p.17
10	14/5/1992	Zango-Kataf	Kaduna	Hausa/Fulani and Southern Zaria Christians	Many were killed including the Zaria CAN secretary, ECWA Vice President, & Baptist Rev.	Today's Challenge, No.1. 1992,p.1-14
11	9/9/1996	Kaduna polytechnic	Kaduna	Shiite Islamic sect	It claimed so many lives including that of a police inspector and a soldier.	Odey John 2000, p39

After the first two decades comes another form of jihad prosecuted by Boko Haram. In the second decades which cover 2000 to date, Nigeria has suffered insurgence that gradually metamorphosing into Fulani herdsmen killer group. Lamenting the killings by the herdsmen in Taraba and other States in Nigeria, the former

Chief of Army Staff, Gen. T.Y. Danjuma urged indigenes of the affected areas to defend themselves. He said,

There is an attempt at ethnic cleansing in the state and of course, some rural state s in Nigeria. We must resist it. We must stop it. Every one of us

must rise up. Our Armed Forces are not neutral. They collude with the bandit to kill people, kill Nigerians. The Armed Forces guide their movements; they cover them. If you are depending on the Armed Forces to stop the killings, you will all die one by one. This ethnic cleansing must stop in Taraba State and other rural states of Nigeria otherwise Somalia will be a child's play. I ask every one of you to defend yourselves because you have no other place to go. God bless our country (Daily sun 29/3/2018: 48).

Explanations proffered for the frequent occurrences of ethno-religious violence in Nigeria are varied. For some it is the inability or unwillingness of those in government to deal firmly with the culprits (Umechukwu 1995). But government claims its sabotage. Archbishop Chukwuemeka Kalu-Uche of the Methodist Church saw it as an attempt to Islamize Nigeria. Hence, he cautioned that "What happened in Turkey cannot happen in Nigeria" (Kalu-Uche, Mar 27th 2018).

Implication of Ethno-Religious Conflicts

Admittedly, Nigeria is at the cross road and blame game would never solve the problem. Some of the implications of ethno-religious conflicts include among other things, the deep distrust that has continued to grow day by day among the Nigerian people. Hence, for over a century, the various ethnic groups have not been

flexible enough to assimilate the culture of other tribal groups.

Ethno-religious conflict is a menace that is threatening the very foundation of Nigeria's cooperate existence as a nation. It is fast eroding the core socio-cultural and religious value which forbids murder, covetousness, falsehood etc. Sequel to senseless killings innocent people and wanton destruction of property in the country some differed considerably from hypocritical position of one Nigeria and are agitating for secession, while others are called for restructuring.

It is incontrovertibly true that ethno-religious conflict is one of the major obstacles to the meaningful development in Nigeria. The heat generated by the conflict does not allow the foreign investors to come and invest in Nigeria for fear of attack. This is affecting the Nation's economy so badly and by extension the citizens. Some company that were affected are struggling to bounce back, while others have become extinct, thereby inhibiting the growth of Nigeria economy as well as well limiting job opportunities. Indeed, where ethnocentrism and religious bigotry are thriving corrupt persons make away with their crimes as each groups try to protect their own irrespective of his/her crime. Thus, integrity and is marred and injustice enthroned.

Way Forward

From 1980 when the extremists started attacking innocent citizens till date, government has treated the issue with laxity. No one has ever been prosecuted for the murder; hence, the attack has continued unabated. This research paper admonishes government to rise to her responsibility to protect the lives and property of its citizens. Perpetrators of the massacres must be brought to justice as murderers. In as much as the country must be together, citizens should imbibe the religious virtues which are embedded on “love for ones neighbour” and “peace with all men”. Citizens should be educated to know that Nigeria nation is an amalgamation of different kingdoms that are virtually different in all ramifications. Hence, tolerance of other people’s culture, religion, and values are of essence.

Every citizen should be treated equal and any misunderstanding arising from religion, politics or cultural differences should be resolved through dialogue. The difference in should de-emphasised while the similarities in the Nigerian people’s cultures and religions should be emphasised to promote peacefully co-existence. Leaders must be Patriotic, honest, religious and diligence so other could learn from them. Patriotism which is love of fatherland is part of the religious virtue of piety. True piety means respect and devotion not only to God and parents

but also to one’s country”. Leaders should show respect and thorough observation of federal character system to avoid marginalization

Conclusion

Religion has been wrongly used by some ethnic groups to afflict this country severally with conflicts leading to wanton destruction of properties and loss of human lives. Obviously, there have been too much blood letting in this country resulting from ethnic and religious conflict which is threatening the very foundation of Nigeria’s cooperate existence as a nation. The menace of ethno-religious conflict in Nigeria is fast eroding the core socio-cultural and religious value which forbids murder, covetousness, falsehood etc. Until ethnic and religious differences are resolved, there may not be a safe country that bears the dreams of slogan of ‘our heroes past’ (One Nigeria, one Nation). From every indication, what is obtainable today is “one Nigeria, many nations.

References

- Adefila, S.A. (2000). *Tithing a Gateway into Divine Abundance*. Illorin; INDEMAC Publishers
- Adinuba, C.D (2014) Stoking Fire with Religious Politics, *The Guardian*, November 7
- Akuma, J.E. (2004). *Islam in Perspective*. Aba Assemblies of God Press
- Awolowo, O. (1947). *Path to Nigerian Freedom*, London: Faber and Faber

- Buah, F.K. (1977). *History Note West Africa Since A.D. 1000: Book two, the People and Outsiders*. London, Macmillan
- (Chukwuemeka Kalu-Uche, mar 27th 2018). Prelate of the Methodist church of Nigeria in a 7 day apostolic tour of the Arch-Diocese of Abuja, Nyanya and Kubua. He backed Danjuma comments that Nigerians should defend themselves.
- Ejor, A.D. (1989). *Reminiscence*, Malthous Press Ltd
- Ene, O.E. (2001). *The Islamic Philosophy; the Nigerian Experience*. Enugu: Jovel Computer Ventures
- Ezeanya, C.P. (2016). *Roots of Public unrest in Nigeria in Eze-Uzoamaka 2016 Nigerian peoples and culture*. Enugu. Parakletos Immunnis Derive
- Global Jihad Network 2013. http://www.globaljihad.net/view_page.asp
- International Crisis Group (2013). *Curbing Violence in Nigeria: The Jos Crisis, Africa Report*
- Jibrin Ibrahim, (1989). "Politics of religion in Nigeria: The Parameters of the 1987 Crisis in Kadana State", *Review of African Political Economy*, 45, 65-82. pp. 65–68, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4006011>, accessed on 01/11/2011
- Nzomiwu, J.P.C (1989) *The History and Message of Islam*. Awka, Nigeria MEKS-Unique Publishers
- Obiezuofu-Ezeigbo, A.C. (2007). *The Biafran War and the Igbo in Contemporary Nigeria Politics*; GP Genlus Press
- Ody J.O. (2000). *The Sharia and rest of use*. Enugu; Snaap Press Ltd
- Okonkwo, M.N. (2003). *In The Bowels of Biafra*. Enugu; Vougasen Ltd
- Oritsejifar, A. (2004). *Nationalism and Politics of National Security: The Christian and the Boko Haram Challenge*; Enugu Eminota Nig. Lited
- Osukwu, E.C, (2014). *Ethnic and Religious Differences in Nigeria: The Implications to the Nation's Security and Democratic Rule*
<https://www.worldpulse.com/en/community/users/celine/posts/15622> available 15/5/2018
- Yinka Odumakin <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2016/07/as-it-was-in-1953/>
(Uka 2008). *Ethnic, Religious and Communal Conflict in Nigeria: Implications for security*. In Ituma 2008 *Professor Bassey Andah Journal of Cultural Studies Vol. 1*. Umuahia. Glorious Dawn Sylva Co
- Umechukwu, O.J. (1995). *The Press Coverage of Religious Voilence in nigeria*. Enugu; Ugovin Publishers
- Yusuf, T. (1982). *Socio-Political Role and Status of Non-Muslim Groups of Northern Nigeria: Analysis of Colonial Legacy*. Ph.D Thesis. Boston.